

Epigraphy.info X Workshop: Final Report

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Next workshop:

Spring 2027, Annie Burman, Uppsala University in Sweden

The current Steering Committee members [2026-2027]:

- Silvia Evangelisti, University of Foggia, IT
- Annie Burman, Uppsala University, SWE
- Andrea Santamaria, Kiel University, DE
- Anna Clara Maniero Azzolini, University of London, GB
- Matthias Scholler, Graz University, AUT
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Epigraphy.info community on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/epigraphy-info/>

Link to the report from the Epigraphy IX <https://zenodo.org/records/15705466>

Link to collaborative Google document [📄 Epigraphy.info X - collaborative document](#)

Introduction

[Epigraphy.info](#) is an international, open community that fosters a collaborative environment for digital epigraphy, facilitating scholarly communication and interaction. Epigraphy.info applies FAIR principles to epigraphic information, enabling the efficient creation, use, and sharing of it among researchers, students, and enthusiasts worldwide. The Epigraphy.info community works to gather and enhance the many existing epigraphic efforts and serves as a landing point for digital tools, practices and methodologies for managing collections of inscriptions.

The Epigraphy.info workshop traditionally brings together researchers and enthusiasts of digital epigraphy to discuss the current trends and issues of the discipline. The meeting includes academic presentations on various topics in digital epigraphy and challenges of the current research, a poster session, as well as training hands-on sessions and workshops/hackathons of the existing working groups and interactive roundtables. It provides a safe space for networking, learning, developing new collaborations, and cutting-edge research in ancient studies, expanding the discipline's focus beyond the traditional Greek and Latin epigraphy. Since the establishment of Epigraphy.info in 2018, there have been nine international meetings: Heidelberg, DE, 2018; Zadar, CRO, 2018; Vienna, AUT, 2019; Hamburg, DE, 2020; Leuven (online), BE, 2020; Princeton (online), US, 2021; Leuven, BE, 2023; Berlin, DE, 2024, Aarhus, DK, 2025.

The tenth Epigraphy.info workshop took place in Graz (Austria) from 24 to 26 March 2026; see the website at https://epigraphy.info/workshop_10. The event was organised by the Department of Classics, Section Ancient History and Epigraphy of the University of Graz, in collaboration with the Epigraphy.info Steering Committee. The tenth Epigraphy.info workshop was dedicated to the memory of Winfried Kumpitsch (1993–2025). It featured a special thematic focus on Sacred Spaces, Sacred Words: Digital Approaches to Religious Epigraphy, an area to which Winfried devoted much of his scholarly work and research. Alongside this theme, the workshop continued the established tradition of bringing together scholars, students, and practitioners of digital epigraphy to exchange ideas, share experiences, and develop new collaborations.

A total of 76 participants registered for the Epigraphy.info X, including 41 in-person and 35 online attendees. The in-person participants represent remarkable diversity, coming from 18 different universities and research centers located in Asia, Europe, and North America: Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Japan, Italy, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Ukraine, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America. Some of the presentations and talks were streamed online, and some parts of the programme allowed for remote attendance, i.e. working group meetings.

DAY 1: 24 March 2026

On the morning of 24 March, the workshop opened with a welcome speech and practical information from the local committee, followed by two sessions of presentations, chaired by Georgios Tsolakis and Silvia Evangelisti, respectively.

Session 1 opened with three papers:

1. Rebecca Benefiel, Sara Sprenkle, and Micah Tongen, who presented ongoing work on *The Ancient Graffiti Project* (<https://ancientgraffiti.org/Graffiti/>), focusing on the development of a search tool for identifying sacred content among Pompeian graffiti. The discussion addressed the practical utility of large language models, noting that whilst different models perform better on certain tasks, their dynamic nature means that human verification remains essential; the potential of agentic use for discrete tasks and the challenge of hallucinations were also raised.
2. Matthias Scholler then introduced the project FERCAN and the editor Patrimonium in the context of Celtic divine names in the inscriptions of Germania Inferior and Superior (<https://gams.uni-graz.at/context/fercan>), with discussion focusing on the potential implementation of RDF and the development of controlled vocabularies.
3. The session concluded with Csaba Szabó and Tünde Vágási presenting ReMITHRA (<https://roman-mithras.hu/>), a digital database of Mithraic monuments from the Danubian provinces (in progress); the discussion centred on handling uncertainty and on the fundamental question of how to define an object within the database, whether a mithraeum, its paintings, or individual items within it.

After a short break, **Session 2** commenced with two papers:

1. Viktor Humennyi outlined a proposed interactive digital dashboard for Roman military epigraphy of Roman Syria (1st–3rd c. CE), discussing design principles for visualising epigraphic distributions. The discussion raised key questions about scope and design, whether another database is needed, what should be included, and how to define military context, and also addressed the treatment of Aramaic inscriptions, noting that transcriptions currently rely on Latin script with diacritics (as in the Dura-Europos project), whilst digital fonts for the original scripts are in development but not yet in use for published inscriptions.
2. Anna Loro then presented her work towards a digital corpus called ‘φωνούμενα’, addressing the encoding of vase inscriptions and the particular challenges they pose for standard epigraphic markup. Loro’s presentation prompted discussion on several fronts: the challenge of nonsense inscriptions, sequences of letters, typically omicron and lambda, owing to their ease of painting, or other combinations that yield no meaningful word, and the question of how to integrate the database with the Corpus Vasorum Antiquorum, as well as the attribution of inscriptions to a potter or a painter.

The lunch break was followed by a **poster session** with 10 posters, which brought together a wide range of projects, from corpus creation to the application of computer-assisted methods in their analysis, including LLM. The poster session ran from 14:00-14:45. All posters can be accessed and downloaded from the [Epigraphy.info](https://epigraphy.info) website. Authors were offered the option to publish their contributions as part of the [Zenodo Epigraphy.info community](https://zenodo.org/communities/epigraphy.info), each assigned a unique DOI for citation and long-term accessibility.

1. Maria Rosaria Ariano proposed a digital workflow for analysing out-of-context inscriptions, illustrated through a votive dedication from eastern Sicily.
2. Caterina Borgatti, Marta Fogagnolo, and Giuseppina Viscardi presented the digital Lexicon LARES, a resource for religious epigraphy.
3. Olmo Ceriotti, Federico Gerardi, Saverio Giulio Malatesta, and Silvia Orlandi contributed to a poster on language modelling for epigraphs, using EDR datasets.
4. Miroslav Čovan and Anna Barnau Gerardi demonstrated the Corpus Inscriptionum Slovaciae, a digital portal incorporating AI-powered inscription detection.
5. Jeffrey Garcia presented an approach to sequential constraint-elimination in the analysis of fragmentary inscriptions, using a test case from the Athenian Agora.
6. Marietta Horster, David Eibeck, and Francisca Feraudi-Gruénais introduced the EDEp Editor.
7. Christoph Klose offered reflections on objects as information carriers.
8. Gevorg Nersesian, Suren Khachatryan, and Narine Sarvazyan reported on advances in Armenian inscription recognition.
9. Jun Ogawa evaluated large language models for the automatic generation of EpiDoc TEI from Leiden transcriptions.
10. Andrea Santamaria and Eleonora Selvi provided a preliminary overview of a corpus of inscriptions in the local languages of Thrace.

Session 3, chaired by Matthias Scholler, opened after the poster session.

1. Hamest Tamrazyan illustrated how the descriptive terminology of Ukrainian sacred inscriptions can be formalised within a structured digital vocabulary. Drawing on the cultural semantics of sacred writing, the research eschews generic typologies (such

as “funerary” or “dedicatory”) to reconstruct the authentic structure of local scholarly discourse and devotional practice. The work demonstrates that this terminology itself constitutes a form of intangible cultural heritage: encoding it via the SKOS standard serves to preserve not only the epigraphic records, but the entire conceptual and theological universe that gave them meaning.

2. Aleksandra Kubiak-Schneider examined the current underrepresentation of Aramaic religious epigraphy in the digital sphere, presenting a methodological solution through the Linked Open Data (LOD) approach and Wikidata. Focusing on the uniquely multilingual landscape of Dura-Europos, the presentation illustrated the interaction between Aramaic, Greek, and Latin within sacred spaces. By demonstrating how LOD can interconnect inscriptions, individuals, and architectural contexts, such as the temples of Atargatis, Adonis, and Bel, the work underscores the importance of integrating Aramaic into digital classical epigraphy. This research is conducted within the framework of the International (Digital) Dura-Europos Archive (IDEA) project. <https://duraeuroposarchive.org/>

The afternoon concluded with a **practical session** led by Anna Clara Maniero Azzolini and Pietro Ortimini on recording inscriptions in Wikidata and Wikibase, giving participants hands-on experience with linked open data approaches to epigraphic documentation. Supporting materials included a shared Google Spreadsheet (<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OJG8ATq8L17d383IGxhm2NruOzVj3THBYvfHlrTSjHo/>) and a mapping of EDR fields and values to Wikidata properties (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/User:Anna_Clara_Maniero_Azzolini/Altinum#Mapping_EDR_fields_and_values_with_Wikidata). Participants worked directly with Wikidata (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page), including the creation of new items (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Special:NewItem>). Those editing Cyrenaica inscriptions were advised to add a reference to the Greek Metrical Inscriptions database using the 'described at URL' property (see e.g. <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q138780701>). The session also introduced the Wikibase instance for Greek Metrical Inscriptions (https://greek-metrical-inscriptions.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Main_Page).

The day ended with **working group meetings**, which were also open to remote attendance (communications WG; ontology/vocabularies WG; funding WG). The representatives of each working group reported on the meetings during the community discussion on DAY 3.

DAY 2: 25 March 2026

Session 4, chaired by Rebecca Benefiel, opened the morning with three presentations on digital methods and artificial intelligence in epigraphy.

1. Petra Heřmánková and Marietta Horster, with Jonathan Prag and Imran Asif participating in absentia, presented the results of the FAIR Epigraphy Project (2022–2026), reporting on progress towards linked open data in epigraphic practice and the project's outcomes, available at inscriptions.org and the project's GitHub repository. The presentation, available with interactive links at <http://bit.ly/FAIRepi26>, was accompanied by a recent article: Heřmánková, Petra, Imran Asif, Marietta Horster, and Jonathan R. W. Prag (2025), "From Fragmented Data to Linked History: Developing the FAIR Epigraphic Vocabularies," *Journal of Open Humanities Data*

- 11(1), <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.428>. The presenters invited the audience to participate in an ongoing survey scoping current community needs in order to inform future developments and activities.
2. Georgios Tsolakis then offered a critical assessment of ChatGPT and Claude as tools for the study of Greek epigraphic cultures, evaluating the capabilities and limitations of large language models in this domain, especially when focusing on the classification of inscriptions.
 3. Michael Satlow concluded the session with a presentation on using AI to encode inscriptions, reflecting on practical workflows and outcomes. <https://www.inscriptionsisraelpalestine.org/>. Satlow demonstrated his application (available via GitHub at <https://bit.ly/4bcArqu>), which uses Claude via the API; whilst the API tokens must be purchased, the cost per token is relatively low; cheaper, as he noted, than hiring a student.

After a short break, **Session 5**, chaired by Andrea Santamaria, brought together three presentations spanning a broad geographical and chronological range, beyond the ancient Mediterranean.

1. Manuel Sassmann presented a cross-media publishing project on Buddhist stone sutras in China and its pursuit of a sustainable digital legacy. The Stone Sutras project is a Heidelberg-based initiative running since 2004 that is now being redeveloped with LOD and FAIR principles in mind, including an EdEp-like editor tailored to Chinese inscriptions. Further information is available at <https://www.stonesutras.org/home.html>.
2. Lia Wei examined medieval Taoist cliff inscriptions and their modern reception, with particular attention to descriptive vocabularies for inscribed landscapes, calligraphic variation, and rubbings. Wei presented the Altergraphy project (<https://altergraphy.hypotheses.org/>), which addresses medieval Taoist cliff inscriptions and their modern reception, developing descriptive vocabularies for inscribed landscapes, calligraphic variation, and rubbings. The project draws on OpenTheso (<https://opentheso.huma-num.fr/index.xhtml>) for thesaurus management.
3. Hamest Tamrazyan, Gayane Hovhannisyan, and Arsen Harutyunyan closed the session by discussing the alignment of Armenian epigraphic conventions with the Leiden and EpiDoc frameworks, accompanying a newly published article by Tamrazyan et al. (2026), "From Stone to Standards: A Digital Heritage Interoperability Model for Armenian Epigraphy Within the Leiden and EpiDoc Frameworks" (<https://www.mdpi.com/2571-9408/9/1/27>). The presentation also introduced ArmEpiC: the Armenian Epigraphic Corpus, including the ArtsakhEpiC sub-corpus (v1.0), available on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/18206503>). The discussion that followed underscored the broader importance of aligning national and regional epigraphic traditions with shared community standards.

Following the lunch break, Gregor Diez led the **second practical session**, introducing participants to Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) as a method for restoring the readability of inscriptions through optical analysis, and then demonstrating the equipment and the process in practice. Dataset Optical Diagnostics in Epigraphy available at <https://repository.tugraz.at/records/4pk9w-pc814>.

After a short break, Wolfgang Spickermann delivered the **keynote lecture** “*Perspectives on digital epigraphy: small inscriptions and technical visualization*”. Spickermann's keynote surveyed current perspectives on digital epigraphy, drawing on a range of projects and tools. These included the Graz database of ancient epigraphy (<https://gams.uni-graz.at/context:age>), the CEIPAC project on amphorae inscriptions (<https://ceipac.ub.edu/>), the Thedefix project on defixiones based at the University of Hamburg (<https://www.geschichte.uni-hamburg.de/arbeitsbereiche/alte-geschichte/digitalisierung/thedefix.html>), the RTI viewer developed by CNR (<https://vcg.isti.cnr.it/~palma/rti/rtiviewer.php>), and the Ithaca and Aeneas tools for predictive restoration and attribution of ancient inscriptions (<https://predictingthepast.com/>).

The day concluded with a **guided tour** of the Gipsabgussammlung and a reception held at the same venue.

Day 3: 26 March 2026

Session 6, chaired by Annie Burman, opened the morning of the day's proceedings with three presentations.

1. Mariana Bodnaruk examined epigraphic networks of office and religious affiliation among the fourth-century Palatine elite, drawing on digital methods to analyse patterns of social and devotional identity, with reference to the PPRET Inscriptions resource (<http://ppret-inscriptions.huma-num.fr>), directed by P. Porena with contributions from E. Angius, A. Bernier, G. Franceschini, and I. Vagionakis (Strasbourg: MISHA, 2022).
2. Anna Fitiskina and Vladimir Ippolitov then presented a digital approach to Old East Slavic epigraphy spanning the eleventh to fifteenth centuries, addressing the particular challenges of corpus-building for this material, drawing on gramoty.ru, epigraphica.ru. The inscription <https://epigrafika.ru/epigraphy/inscription/show/128> was displayed as an example.
3. The session concluded with Dimitar Iliev and Kristiyan Simeonov, who described the creation of a pilot digital corpus of Old Church Slavonic inscriptions, presenting the Epigraphia Slavica project (<https://tinyurl.com/epigraphia-slavica>) alongside related tools including Telamon (<https://telamon.uni-sofia.bg/>), Tituli (<http://tituli.naim.bg/>), and a GitHub repository with a Streamlit visualisation tool (<http://linktr.ee/Bashtina>).

Community discussion and decisions, elections

The second morning session was dedicated to community discussion and reports from the working groups, community decisions, and most importantly, the Steering Committee election and choosing of the organiser of the next meeting in 2027.

Next workshop:

There was one candidate for the local organiser of the Epigraphy.info XI workshop. The community has approved that the next workshop will be organised by Annie Burman of Uppsala University in Sweden. The exact date will be communicated later, but presumably in spring 2027.

The Steering Committee election:

As three steering committee members were stepping down (Georgios Tsolakis and Rebecca Benefiel), the community had to select three new members. In the end, three candidates are elected as new members: Anna Clara Maniero Azzolini, Matthias Scholler and Dimitar Illiev. The new Steering Committee has therefore 6 members, including a local organiser of the next workshop:

- Silvia Evangelisti, University of Foggia, IT
- Annie Burman, Uppsala University, SWE
- Andrea Santamaria, Kiel University, DE
- Anna Clara Maniero Azzolini, University of London, GB
- Matthias Scholler, Graz University, AUT
- Dimitar Illiev, Sv. Kliment Ohridski University in Sofia, BG

Ontology & Vocabularies Working Group Report:

- Petra Heřmánková continues as the point person for the group.
- Activities organised by the FAIR Epigraphy Project (concluded 02/2026), updated EpOnt ontology published (J. Prag), new vocabularies and several others in progress (P. Heřmánková), see more at <https://inscriptions.org/>
- An ongoing survey until the end of April 2026 to assess the needs of the community and make a strategic plan; members were encouraged to complete.
- In response to a question from Jonathan Prag on the rationale for an ontology, the discussion clarified that an ontology becomes necessary when researchers wish to share and combine data across datasets, as it provides the organisational structure and hierarchy required for interoperability.
- Petra will circulate an email in the first half of the year regarding upcoming meetings of the WG; those wishing to be added to the mailing list should provide their name and email address.

Communication & Outreach Working Group Report:

- The working group welcomed four new members: Caterina Borgatti, Marta Fogagnolo, Davide Massimo, and Aleksandra Kubiak-Schneider. All members of the [Epigraphy.info](https://epigraphy.info) community are encouraged to update the member list with their current project or institution affiliation. Projects wishing to be featured on social media via the EpigraphyTuesday initiative should send relevant content to communication@epigraphy.info.
- On infrastructure, a crowdfunding event allowed for collecting funds to cover [Epigraphy.info](https://epigraphy.info) hosting until November 2028 (at the current cost of 35 EUR/year, at United Domains, DE; managed by Petra Heřmánková).
- The community is also invited to contribute to a report on the history of [Epigraphy.info](https://epigraphy.info), how it started and how it has developed, coordinated by Chiara Cenati with input from Steering Committee members. Contributions are welcome from all members regardless of how long they have been involved, as a diversity of perspectives is considered valuable.
- Finally, the group discussed establishing contact with Jens Bartels in Zurich regarding a potential community-level link with the Clauss-Slaby database.

Funding Working Group Report:

- Marietta Horster: The working group may no longer be necessary in its current form. Scholars seeking a letter of support from Epigraphy.info when applying for funding should direct requests to the Steering Committee rather than the Funding group; the community should be clearly informed of this.